

European Air Pollution Exposure Maps (EXPANSE / UBDPolicy)

This record documents the generation of high-resolution European air pollution exposure maps developed within the EXPANSE framework and extended to cover the period 2020–2024 in the context of UBDPolicy.

Input data and modelling framework

Air pollution models were developed using routinely available measurement station data combined with a comprehensive set of spatiotemporal predictor variables, including land use, traffic indicators, population density, elevation, satellite-derived NO₂, aerosol optical depth (AOD), and NDVI, and meteorological variables.

Outputs

The main outputs are European-wide exposure maps for multiple air pollutants, produced as high-resolution geospatial datasets of each country. Approximate data volumes for the total full-Europe annual surfaces are:

NO₂: ~29 GB per year

O₃: ~37.8 GB per year

PM₁₀: ~29.5 GB per year

PM_{2.5}: ~26.7 GB per year

Data access

Due to data volume and licensing considerations, the exposure maps and associated datasets are not distributed directly via Zenodo. Access is provided through the EXPANSE project infrastructure.

All data requests and further information are available via the EXPANSE Exposome Maps toolbox:

<https://expansoproject.eu/toolbox/exposome-maps/>